

Effectiveness of Community – School Relations Policy on Safety of Students in Boarding High Schools in Homa Bay County

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Abstract:- Safety of students among learners in public high schools has been a great challenge globally. This is a phenomenon that has greatly affected public secondary school students in Kenya. Despite the launch of Safety and Standards manual for secondary schools in the year 2008, with the expectation that implementations of community – school relations policy would ensure that students would be safe, media reported cases of community threats due to sour relationships between the school and the community. The objective of this study was to establish the effectiveness of community – school relations policy on safety of students in Boarding high Schools in Homa Bay County. Both correlational and Descriptive research designs were used. 34 Principals, 8 Sub County Quality Assurance and Standards Officers (SCQASOs) and 4,800 students formed the population. 31 Principals and 8 SCQASOs and 369 students were sampled for the study. Research tools used to collect data included, students’ focus group discussions, observation schedule/document analysis guide and interviews schedules. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze quantitative data. Thematically, qualitative data was analyzed. The study revealed that community – school relations policy had statistically significant effect on safety of students since $p < 0.05$ and contributed 71.0% of the variation in safety of students. There was a strong and positive effect of community – school relations policy on safety of students of 0.848 at p – value of 0.01.

Keywords:- Effectiveness, Safety Policy, Community – School Relations, Homa Bay County, Safety of students, Kenya, Boarding High Schools.

I. INTRODUCTION

Community – school relations focus on how learners, teaching staff, non-teaching staff and the school administration are viewed and treated by the communities within which schools are located and vice versa. A conducive school climate needs to be created by the learners and staff for other stakeholders to be involved in a wide range of school activities (Republic of Kenya, 2008).

Mgijima (2014) carried out a study on violence experienced in South African Schools: Perception of Communities on a persistent problem and established poor parental participation prevented successful implementation of intervention strategies. Communities need to be mobilized, empowered and equipped with relevant knowledge and skills to stimulate appropriate action in their endeavor to reduce violence in schools. Sekiwu and Kabanda (2014) in a study on building safer secondary schools in Uganda through

collective commitment to health and safety compliance revealed a positive relationship between collective commitment and managed health and safety and the relationship was found to be significant ($r = 0.567$, $p \leq 0.01$). In conclusion, the study recommended that collective involvement of stakeholders would ensure health and safety in Ugandan secondary schools for in which the community is part. This finding concurred with those of Mgijima (2014) however; the study was specific to collective involvement in ensuring health and safety in Ugandan Schools but did not look at community – school relation policy and its effectiveness on safety of students.

Wilson (nd) conducted a study on the effect of community involvement programs on school violence also established that community involvement programs that were statistically significant according to the data were the involvement programs that incorporated social services, juvenile justice and law enforcement. This study was specific to violence as a safety concern and majorly based on the community’s role without looking at the role played by both the community and the school in enhancing safety of students. The current study therefore focused on determining the effectiveness of community – school relations policy on safety of students in Boarding high Schools in Homa Bay County.

In Kenya, a study was carried out by International Labour Organization (2013), entitled “situational analysis on conducive learning environment for children withdrawn and prevented from child labour”, and established that there was inadequate support to the schools by the community. In some cases, the community had failed to undertake a distinct role to support children affected by child labour or school management. However, the support of the community had been realized in form of local Child Based Organizations (C.B.Os) and Non-Governmental Organizations (N.G.Os) providing support towards school fee payment for needy children and further support with scholastic materials. This study looked at the community with aim to creating school environment which is conducive for children withdrawn or prevented from child labour and did not include all the students. The current study however, sought to look at the effectiveness of implementation of community – school relations policy on safety of students in boarding high schools in Homa Bay County. This study covered a much larger region than Busia District in the previous study hence would give a wider perspective.

Migiro (2012), sought to investigate implementation of the recommended safety standards in Public Secondary Schools in Borabu District. It was revealed from the study that most of the schools organized meetings regularly with the parents; however, very few schools were found to organize joint social-cultural activities with the communities. This finding did not capture many other aspects of community – school relation safety and therefore could not be generalized to the schools in Kenya. Further, this study did not establish the effectiveness of community – school relation policy on safety of students in Boarding high Schools in Homa Bay County. The knowledge gap this study sought to bridge.

Omondi (2016) conducted a study on the influence of students conflicts on community – school relations in Vihiga Sub – County, Kenya and established that conflicts were found to strain the relationship between the school and the community, since such conflicts normally spill over to the community around the school, although the community is always ready to assist the school in case of students’ conflicts. Whereas this study majored on how students’ conflicts influence school- community relations, the current study sought to establish the effectiveness of community – school relations policy on safety of students in Boarding high Schools in Homa Bay County.

Muthoni (2015) conducted a study to investigate the impact of community involvement in Public Secondary Schools Management in Machakos County, Kenya, and established that most of the members of the community would attend meetings organized by the school to which they were invited. It was further established that only few parents assisted their students with school work while very few

members of the community were able to discuss school matters with the students. The study also established that only a smaller number of the communities participated in the process of decision making in these schools, meaning that very few of them were in a position to initiate school projects. This study majorly focused on the impact of community involvement in management of Public Secondary Schools which was too general unlike the current study which looked at the effectiveness of community – school relations policy on safety of the students which is specific on management of safety of students. Good relationship with the school would indeed improve the level of safety of the students, however, this may not have been achieved in this study due to the fact that only minority of the community were involved in decision making. Moreover, this study has not given the actual effectiveness of the community involvement as the study only adopted descriptive research design which could not give the effectiveness, a gap this study sought to fill in Boarding high Schools in Homa Bay County.

II. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

To establish the effectiveness of community – school relations policy on safety of students in Boarding high Schools in Homa Bay County.

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The conceptual framework used below shows that when community – school relations policy is implemented, safety of students is guaranteed. Safety standards manual indicated that when the guidelines are put in place, the learners would be safe in their schools (Republic of Kenya, 2008).

Fig. 1: A Conceptual Framework showing the Effectiveness of Community - school relations policy on Safety of Students in Boarding high Schools

(Source: Author)

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study used both correlational and descriptive survey research designs and was done in Homa Bay County,

in boarding high schools. Principals (34), students (4800) and Sub County Quality Assurance and Standards Officers (8) formed the study population. Sampling was done as per table 1 below:

Table 1: Sample Frame

Respondents	Target Population (N)	Sample Size (n)
SCQASOs	8	8
Principals	34	31
Students	4, 800	369
TOTAL	4, 876	408

Source: Author

Sample size was determined by Yamane Taro’s Formula (Yamane, 1967):

$$n_y = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where:

n_y = Yamane Sample size;

N = Underlying population

e = Determined from the confidence level e.g. $e = 0.05$ for being 95% sure about the results. (The error of 5% points)

Data collection was done using focus group discussions guide, observation schedule/ document analysis guide and interviews schedule. Both face and content validity of the tools were determined by research experts in Educational Administration. Piloting the instruments was done in 3 schools to establish their reliability, as recommended by Mugenda and Mugenda, (2003). In order to determine the reliability of the instruments, Cronbach’s Alpha was used and a coefficient of 0.935 was obtained as shown in Table 2.

a) Case Processing Summary

Table 2: Chronbach’s Alpha Calculation

		N	%
Cases	Valid	2	66.7
	Excluded ^a	1	33.3
	Total	3	100.0

a. List wise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

b) Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.935	85

Source: Field Data

From Table 2, Cronbach’s alpha (α) coefficient of 0.935 was considered to be excellent as suggested by Holton, Brownlow, McMurray, and Cozens (2004), who suggested four points of reliability with coefficient of above 0.90 (excellent) and therefore the instrument was reliable. Data analysis was done both quantitatively and qualitatively.

V. RESULTS

The implementation of community – school relations policy and safety of students status were established and results tabulated as shown in Table 3 and Table 4.

Table 3: Status of Implementation of Community –School Relations Policy as per Researcher’s Observation (n = 31)

Community - School relations policy Aspects		Ratings					Total Score	MR
		1	2	3	4	5		
Linkage between school and community	F	0	2	3	21	5	122	3.94
Attitude of students and staff towards the community	F	0	6	16	5	4	100	3.23
Behavior towards community	F	0	6	13	10	2	101	3.26
Academic meetings and the community	F	0	8	12	10	1	97	3.12
Co curriculum and cultural activities	F	6	10	14	1	0	72	2.32
Participation in community activities	F	2	9	2	10	8	106	3.42
School development effort	F	0	0	3	19	9	130	4.19
Community administrative structure	F	0	2	7	15	7	120	3.87
Sensitization of the community by the school authority	F	0	0	2	18	11	133	4.29
OMR	F	8	43	72	109	47	983	3.52

KEY: MR: Mean Rating OMR: Overall Mean Rating F: Frequency

Source: Field Data

- 1.00- 1.44 = Not Accomplished,
- 1.45 – 2.44 = Less Accomplished,
- 2.45 – 3.44 = Moderately Accomplished,
- 3.45 – 4.44 = Partly Accomplished,
- 4.45 – 5.00 = Fully Accomplished

From Table 3, it can be noted that implementation of community – school relations policy with respect to sensitization of the community by the school authority (4.29), school development effort (4.19), linkage between school and community (3.94) and community administrative structure (3.87), were rated as partly accomplished, meaning above average level. Implementation of school – community relations policy with respect to participation in community activities (3.42), behavior towards community (3.26), attitude of students and staff towards the community (3.23) and academic meetings and the community (3.12) were rated as moderately accomplished, meaning at an average status. Organizing co curriculum and cultural activities was rated as less accomplished as shown by mean rating of 2.32.

The rating of sensitization of the community by the school authority at 4.29 meant that it was partly accomplished. Most of the school authorities used local administrative structures to to sensitize the communities on educational needs for their children with special needs. This was made even more possible by involving provincial administration and spiritual leaders in the Board of Management of these schools. Moreover, the school newsletters also carried some information to the community about children with special needs.

The finding that the school development efforts rated 4.19 meant that the community partially supported school development projects. This finding was asserted by a number of principals where one of them stated that:

Parents and the community around the school have given this school an opportunity to be counted among the best schools in the region. Whenever there was a need, parents and the entire community through their leaders were invited to participate in planning. Thereafter, they would always turn up in large numbers for fundraising to

ensure the success of the planned project (Principal 12).

This revelation meant that the community around the school had very good relations with the school, the reason why they supported most of the school activities. However, there are a few schools in which parents were coerced to support school development projects. In such schools, there were elements of conflict between the community and the school as indicated by Omondi (2016), that conflicts were found to strain community – school relationship.

The current study further established that school development efforts were partly accomplished rated at 4.19. Parents and community around the school had recognized the fact that infrastructure development in any school depends on how much the community takes it. This is consistent with the findings of Russel (2009), who established that there is general agreement that community participation contributes to school infrastructure improvement and that it is generally accepted as an output of participation. The findings were also corroborated by Meena (2010), whose study established that community leaders were partially involved (43%) in some managerial functions except in implementing school plans and that the involvement of the community leaders was limited to mobilization for direct voluntary and obligatory contribution of materials, funds, labour force as well as donation and allocation of construction sites. Contrary to this finding, it was established by Adam (2005), that, whereas community participation in education was acclaimed as a good idea by all parents, the fear of intrusion was a major challenge to their desire to participate, and therefore their performance was low. In boarding high schools in Homa Bay County however, the status of implementation for this was partly accomplished.

Linkage between the school and the community was rated at 3.94, meaning it was partly accomplished in boarding high schools in Homa Bay County. It was further revealed that most of the casual workers in schools came from the local community except experts who were employed based on merit, in which case, the locals who met the qualifications

were given priority. This improved the community - school linkage.

The rating of community administrative structure at 3.87 meant that it was partly accomplished. In most of the boarding high schools visited, it was revealed that the community around the school used its administrative structures to resolve community and school conflicts. It was further established that in these schools, the area chiefs and/or assistant area chiefs had very close ties with the schools' administration. The ones in charge of safety, the students in such schools felt safe as their safety was guaranteed. It was therefore established that the community around these schools use their administrative structures to create peace between the schools and the community.

Participation in community activities was rated at 3.42, meaning that it was moderately accomplished. It was clear that most of the schools planned for clean - up activities around the schools per term, though a few would plan twice a term. However, there were also schools that planned once per year and yet others did not do it at all. When students are involved in community service, they learn to be responsible and at the same time, and by so doing, they also make the school surrounding tidy which would improve the safety of students. Thus, in Homa Bay County, participation in community activities was moderately accomplished in public secondary schools.

Behaviour of students and teachers towards the community was moderately accomplished as shown by the mean rating of 3.26. This means that both the staff and the students were respectful to the community near boarding high schools in Homa Bay County. For effective relations to occur both the teachers and the students must behave well towards the community by showing respect to one another and as a result, the community will reciprocate the good will to the school making the students safe.

The rating of attitude of students and staff towards the community being 3.23 was moderately accomplished. This means that it was at an average level. This finding was corroborated by the findings of Gerda and Rene (2007), who established that students with prior knowledge of participation in a community service project were greatly willing to enroll for a course/module in Community Service-Learning, more particularly when it would add value to their career development. This was the level of attitude towards the community. This finding was further corroborated by a student during a focus group discussion who said, "our attitude towards the community is a positive one but not adequate. Some of them don't treat us with respect"

The findings on the academic meetings and the community, was rated at 3.12 meaning moderately accomplished. A close scrutiny of parents' attendance registers of the schools visited revealed that there was low attendance of Form two and Form three parents, but higher attendance of parents were in Form 1 and Form 4. This was true for both open days (when parents share with the individual subject teachers) and during Annual General Meetings. On interrogating Directors (Deans) of Studies, from whose office these records were obtained, it was further established that very few parents would be willing to follow up their son's/daughter's performance. However, it was established that many of these parents would be willing to support academic programs in the school as agreed.

The aspect that was least accomplished as shown by a mean rating of 2.32, was co - curriculum and cultural activities. It was established that such activities are seldom organized. Probably, the only major area where this is organized is when soccer team in a school organizes for a friendly match with a local soccer team. Though this was found to be very rare and instead it is organized between schools. Organizing co curriculum activities and cultural activities should be done frequently to improve the linkage between the school and the community. It was thus least accomplished in boarding high schools in Homa Bay County.

The level of implementation of community - school relations policy had an overall mean rating of 3.52 meaning that community - school relations policy was partly accomplished in boarding high schools in Homa Bay County. The findings were consistent with the findings of Lubuva (2013) in study that looked at parental involvement in school programs management which found out that, parents were involved in school through enrolment campaign, school meetings and physical contribution. Planning, building classrooms, mobilization of financial resources, buying instructional materials, furniture and fund raising was a role played by parents. However, these findings showed that parents were not involved in monitoring and follow-up of the learning process due to lack of understanding and unclear identification activities of parents involved and lack of cooperation with teachers. However, Muthoni (2015) established that a good number of the members of the community attended few meetings to which they were invited.

Table 4: Status of Safety of students in Relation to Community - School Relations Policy as per Researcher’s Observation (n = 31)

Aspects of Safety of students		Ratings					Total Score	MR
		1	2	3	4	5		
Students’ property stolen by members of the community due to poor linkage with the surrounding community;	F	0	0	2	7	22	144	4.65
Low academic performance due to lack of regular joint meetings on academic matters with parents/ guardians;	F	0	0	15	14	2	111	3.58
Unhealthy school surrounding due to lack of participation of students in some community activities such as clean ups;	F	0	3	13	12	3	108	3.48
Lack of infrastructural development due to inactive involvement of the community in school’s development efforts;	F	0	0	14	8	9	119	3.84
School attacked by the community due to school- community land dispute;	F	0	0	28	3	3	96	3.10
OMR	F	0	3	72	44	36	578	3.72

KEY: MR: Mean Rating

OMR: Overall Mean Rating

F: Frequency

Source: Field Data

1.00- 1.44 = Once per Week (Not Safe)

1.45 – 2.44 = Once per Month (Less Safe)

2.45 – 3.44 = Once per Term (Fairly Safe)

3.45–4.44 = Once per Year (More Safe)

4.45 – 5.00 = Nil Occurrence (Very Safe)

From Table 4, it was observed that students were very safe with respect to students’ property stolen by members of the community due to poor linkage with the surrounding community which was highly rated at 4.65. Other aspects of safety of the students in relation to school – community policy including lack of infrastructural development due to inactive involvement of the community in school’s development efforts (3.84), low academic performance due to lack of regular joint meetings on academic matters with parents/ guardians (3.58) and unhealthy school surrounding due to lack of participation of students in some community activities such as clean ups (3.48), were rated as being more safe, whereas the aspect of school being attacked by the community due to school- community land dispute (3.10), was rated as fairly safe.

Students’ property stolen by members of the community due to poor linkage with the surrounding community was highly rated at 4.65. This means that the students were very safe. Whenever there are good relations between the community and the school, the students would be more protected as the surrounding community cannot allow those with ill motive to steal from the school. Thefts that were associated to poor linkage between the school and the community were reported in nine (9) secondary schools in Homa Bay County. However, in most of the schools, there were no theft cases associated with poor linkage and this

could be an indicator of good school community linkage. The students were overall found to be very safe.

Lack of infrastructural development due to inactive involvement of the community in school’s development efforts was rated at 3.84, meaning that the students were more safe. In majority of the schools, twenty-two (22), the students were not very safe with respect to this aspect. However, in nine (9) schools, the students were found to be very safe and the community fully participated in school development activities. Students in boarding high schools were however, found to be more safe with respect to this aspect in Homa Bay County. In most cases, the community around the school plays a pivotal role in improving the structures within the school. Whenever there is good linkage between the school and the community, development of physical facilities in the school is guaranteed.

The rating of low academic performance due to lack of regular meetings on academic matters with parents showed that the students were more safe as rated at 3.58. This rating could be attributed to the fact that parent and the community do not hold regular academic meetings with the school. Indeed, in a very big number of the schools (29), the rating was low meaning that parents rarely visited the schools to discuss their sons’/ daughters’ performance. However, it was revealed that parents had regular academic meetings in some two (2) schools. The students were overall found to be more safe, with respect to this aspect in boarding high schools in Homa Bay County.

A hostile school surrounding due to lack of participation of students in some community activities such as clean - ups was rated at 3.48. Students were therefore more safe. This is a clear revelation of the fact that not so many schools participated in community activities like clean - ups. Only three (3) schools indicated that there was a healthy school surrounding meaning that they participated in community activities. The students were however, found to be more safe in boarding high schools in Homa Bay County.

The rating of school attacked by the community due to school- community land dispute at 3.10 meant that the students were fairly safe. From the ratings, at least all the schools visited had some elements of land dispute. The students were however, fairly safe with respect to this aspect. It is important for school administrators to ensure that the land on which the school is constructed has a valid land

registration and a title deed for the school as this would reduce or clear frequency of attack of the school by the community.

Overall, the students in boarding high schools in Homa Bay County were found to be more safe, with respect to school – community relations policy, as shown by the overall mean rating of 3.72.

To test the hypothesis that: community - school relations policy have no effect on safety of students in boarding high schools in Homa Bay County, simple regression analysis was run at 0.05 significance level. To do this, mean ratings of the status of implementation of community - school relations policy and the mean ratings of status of safety of students were used to run the regression analysis. The results were tabulated as shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Model Summary on Community - School Relations Policy on Safety of students
Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			
						F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.848 ^a	.719	.710	.18759	.719	74.386	1	29	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Community - School Relations Safety

b. Dependent Variable: Safety of students

Source: Field Data

From Table 5, it was revealed that there was a strong and positive effect of school – community relations policy and safety of students of 0.848, which was also found to be statistically significant as $p < 0.05$. Hence the study rejected the null hypothesis that: Community - school relations policy have no effect on safety of students in boarding high schools in Homa Bay County. The adjusted R^2 value of 0.710 implies that the implementation of community - school relations policy accounted for up to 71.0% of the total variance in safety of students in boarding high schools in Homa Bay County. Hence other factors contribute 29.0% in the changes in safety of students. This means that contribution of community - school relations policy on safety of students was above average and good.

Even though the contribution is of a higher percentage of 71.0%, the students were still not very safe with respect to implementation of community - school relations policy. From the observations, it was noticed that implementation of school – community relations policy with respect to co – curriculum and cultural activities was as low as 2.32. On observation, it was noted that this aspect was at most organized once per term as shown by 14 schools, but it was seldom organized or not organized at all. Indeed, community - school interaction is expected to provide the learners in a school the safety and therefore this rating shows that the students were not safe.

Another area of concern was participation in community activities where there was moderate accomplishment meaning that clean-up was done once per year in the neighbouring towns/centers. In some cases, it was irregular or not done at all. By this rating, it meant that the good will that the community would show to the school for participating in community activities wouldn't be there making the students not safe. Moreover, the findings on the safety aspect on unhealthy school surrounding due to lack of participation of students in some community activities like clean ups had a low rating of 3.48 meaning the students were still not safe. During an interview held with one of the principals, the following was said;

Whereas organizing clean - ups around the school is done once in a while by the school administration, class teachers and club and society patrons have also had opportunity to organize clean - ups targeting the market centre, the health facility around the school and the churches. This indeed has greatly improved the safety of the learners (**Principal 5**).

Another principal said:

We have not had an opportunity to join the community in the actual clean - up exercises, but we have been cooperating with them whenever in need of our assistance. We have always given out our plastic chairs for service freely when requested and also offered our school hall for some functions more particularly during school holidays (**Principal 14**).

From the two principals, it was clear that these schools had made good relation with the community, since in one school, clean ups were organized either by the school administration or by class teachers or club leaders with an intention of giving back to the community which makes the community to be positive about the school. On the other hand, offer of school property to be used by the community is another way of improving the community - school relationship. This would in turn improve the safety of the students in these schools. This explains why community – school relations policy, contributes up to 71.0% towards safety of students in boarding high schools in Homa Bay County.

The attitude of the students and the staff towards the community was rated as low as 3.23 with majority of the schools showing that only staff had positive attitude towards the community, while in some six schools, only the administration had positive attitude towards the community. This means that in most of the schools, both the staff and the students had negative attitude towards the community and as a result, the students in boarding high schools were not safe. A principal in one of the schools said that:

The attitude of the staff towards the community around is very positive and this could be seen by incidences when the religious societies within the school are always willing to join other faithful from the local churches. We have always permitted students to join the local church during special programs in the calendar of the churches (**Principal 10**).

On academics, it was established that academic meetings and the community was rated at 3.12 meaning moderately accomplished. It was revealed that in many schools, parents attended open days organized per term per stream of a class to discuss matters academics. Many others only attended open days organized once per class per year meaning least accomplishment. Yet there are parents who only attended academic meetings only once per year and hence making the students not safe in their academics. One of the indicators of safety of students with respect to community – school relations is academic achievement as established by Lubuva (2013) that parental involvement needs to be increased in order to realize higher achievements of educational standards through understanding of the interactions between parenting skills and student success in schooling, participation in school works, and a commitment to consistent communication with teachers about students' progress. The findings of Lubuva (2013) shows that, parents are not involved in monitoring and follow up the learning

process because there is lack of cooperation with teachers, understanding and unclear identification of activities of parental involvement.

The study therefore, found that, parent involvement were not effective. From the data collected, it was revealed that there was low academic performance due to lack of regular joint meetings on academic matters with the parents/guardians. This aspect therefore made the students not safe in boarding high schools in Homa Bay County.

Observation of students behavior and the staff towards the community, established that, in most of the schools, either the staff and students showed above average respect to the community (10) or both the staff and the students showed average respect towards the community. Respect to the community around the school is vital and improves the community - school link, without which, the students are at great risk and hence not safe. The low rating of this aspect at 3.26, as moderately accomplished means that the students in boarding high schools in Homa Bay County were not safe. Another aspect that was a challenge and posed a lot of insecurity to the students was frequent attack of school by the community due to community – school land disputes, where it was established that 28 schools had experienced such dispute at least once per term even when they had title deeds making the students not safe.

Above revelations confirm the fact that community – school policy could account for up to 71.0% of the safety of students in boarding high schools in Homa Bay County.

The high percentage (71.0%) of the contribution by community –school relations policy on the safety of students agrees with the findings of Lubuva (2013), whose study on parental involvement in the management of school programs established that parents were involved in schools through school meetings, enrolment campaigns and physical contribution. The study further established that parents were involved in planning, building classrooms, mobilization of financial resources, buying instructional materials, furniture and fundraising. However, contrary to this higher percentage of the contribution by the community –school relations policy on safety of students, were the findings of Omondi (2016) and Muthoni (2015). Omondi (2015) carried out a study on the influence of students conflicts on school community relations in Vihiga Sub - County, Kenya and established that conflicts were found to strain the relationship between the school and the community, since such conflicts normally spill over to the community around the school even though the community was always ready to assist the school in case of students' conflicts. Muthoni (2015) on the other hand carried out a study on impact of community involvement in public secondary schools' management in Machakos County, Kenya and established that most of the community members attended few meetings on schools' invite and very few parents assisted their sons/ daughters with school homework, while only a small percentage of the community members discussed school matters with the students.

To confirm whether community - school relations policy significantly predict safety of students or not, ANOVA test was run and the results were as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: ANOVA on the Effectiveness of Community - School Relations Policy on Safety of students
ANOVA^b

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	2.618	1	2.618	74.386	.000 ^a
Residual	1.021	29	.035		
Total	3.638	30			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Community - school Relations Safety

b. Dependent Variable: Safety of students

Source: Field Data

From Table 6, it was revealed that community - school relations policy significantly predicted safety of students, (F (1, 29) = 74.386, p = 0.000). This means that implementation of community - school relations policy can be relied on in

enhancing safety of students in boarding high schools in Homa Bay County.

To establish the actual effect, linear regression analysis was computed. The results were as shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Linear Regression on Community - School Relations Policy on Safety of students
Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1 (Constant)	1.034	.342		3.023	.005
School_Community_Safety	.834	.097	.848	8.625	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Safety of students

Source: Field Data

The regression equation is $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X$

Where:

Y is dependent variable (safety of students),

X is independent variable (community - school relations policy),

β_1 is the slope of the regression line and

β_0 is constant (y- intercept) value when x is zero.

From Table 7, it can be observed that one unit increase in implementation of community - school relations policy (**X**) leads to an increase in safety of students by 0.834 units as signified by the coefficient 0.834. This means that the implementation of community –school relations policy is increased by one unit then the safety of the students would be increased by 0.834 units e.g.

$$Y = 1.034 + 0.834 X$$

$$Y = 1.034 + 0.834 (1)$$

$$Y = 1.868 \text{ Units}$$

The findings of this study established that community - school relations policy accounts for 71.0% of the variation in the safety of students. The effect is significant and this means community - school relations policy can be relied on when enhancing the safety of students. The study thus concluded that community - school relations policy had statistically significant effect on safety of students in boarding high schools in Homa Bay County , Kenya.

VI. CONCLUSION

The study established that community –school relations policy had strong and positive effect on safety of students with a coefficient of 0.848 and was also found to be statistically significant as $p < 0.01$. The implementation of community –school relations policy was found to account for up to 71.0% of the variation in safety of students and the implementation was found to be a significant predictor of safety of students, (F (1, 29) = 74.386, $p < 0.05$). A unit increase in implementation of community –school relations policy led to an increase of safety of students by 0.834.

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